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Biodiversity Assessment of Corals Species Present in Mangrove Ecosystems of Silo-Siloan Islet, Clarin, Bohol

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Abstract

*This study governs the population status of corals in Silo-siloan Islet. The main focused of the study were identifying species composition, abundance and diversity of coral species. The sampling was done by sight-seeing and snorkeling in a belt transect covering an area of 100 square meters. Coral species were observed in two sampling sites wherein Site A was located within the mangrove ecosystem while Site B was located outside the mangrove ecosystem. The biodiversity index of the two sites was analyzed using Shannon and Simpson Diversity Indices. Results showed that there were 18 identified coral species in the area namely: *Acropora splendida*, *Acropora insignis*, *Acropora loricata*, *Porites cylindrica*, *Psammocora digitata*, *Millepora alcicornis*, *Pocillopora verrucosa*, *Leptoria phrygia*, *Porites brighami*, *Echinopora lamellosa*, *Turbinaria reniformis*, *Turbinaria peltata*, *Pavona frondifera*, *Fungia fungites*, *Pectinia lactuca*, *Sarcophyton elegans*, *Favites halicora* and *Cycloseris patelliformis*. Among the 18 coral species, the most abundant species was *Pocillopora verrucosa* with 37% abundance. It was observed that most abundant species of corals preferred to thrive in shallow areas and are dependent on irradiance. Shannon diversity index showed that between two sample sites highest diversity index was observed in Site A with 1.8, while Site B had a 1.6 diversity index. However, Simpson Diversity showed that Site B had more dominant coral species than Site A. The result showed the association of mangrove ecosystem to corals. The high diversity of corals within the mangrove ecosystem had shown their greater resiliency towards climate change. Hence, there is a need to conduct further monitoring of water quality for the preservation and sustainability of these unique association of marine ecosystems.*

Keywords: Abundance, Composition, Climate change, Wilderness

I. INTRODUCTION

The Philippines is known to be rich in flora and fauna including coral reefs. Corals or flower animals belonged to Class Anthozoa in the Phylum Cnidaria (Gomez, 1991). Coral studies were of great concern due to its impact on marine organisms. Coral reefs support the diverse association of flora and fauna in the shallow tropical sea. Economically, corals are very important as they are the habitat of fishes and other commercial marine resources. The country is considered home to 3,053 species of fish (Herre, 1953; Allen *et al.*, 2003; Allen and Erdmann 2009), of which 2,724 are marine-based. There are 177 pelagic fish species and 2,351 demersal species. Of these demersal species, 1,658 are associated with coral reefs, and 693 are associated with other nearshore habitats. Scientists estimate that there may be another 1 to 8 million undiscovered species of organisms living in and around reefs (Reaka-Kudla, 1997).

Coral reefs are also considered global centers of biodiversity and are critical for the livelihoods of millions of people that depend on them. Despite this, the health of the coral reefs has been in danger which is caused by a combination of direct human impacts and climate change (Eakin *et al.*, 2008). Warming temperatures and ocean acidification are already affecting coral reefs, causing frequent bleaching events and slowing the formation of coral skeletons. This results in an alteration on the dynamics of marine ecosystems (DA-BFAR, 2004).

They are the first major ecosystem in the world that is seriously damaged because of global climate change. In fact, according to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), the assessment of corals showed that corals are vulnerable to thermal stress and have a low adaptive capacity. Increases in sea surface temperature of about 1–3°C are projected to result in more frequent coral bleaching events and widespread mortality unless there is thermal adaptation or acclimatization by corals.

Worldwide, there are 1000 reef-building species of which 577 species are known in the Philippines (Frail, 2008). Currently, coral reefs including mangroves and water quality, are being degraded in many locations (Alino *et al.*, 2004). As climate change continuously arise, this would possibly leave no more traces of corals in the future. Thus, this study was made to assess resilient coral species that are important in the restoration of coral reefs. Studies of corals documented were more of vulnerability to climate change which

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happened in neighboring countries. There were no studies documented yet in Clarin particularly. Henceforth, the objectives of this study are to monitor the coral reef population and document the current situation in Silo-siloan Islet, a wilderness area part of Clarin neighboring islet. It is uninhabited yet there were reports of illegal fishing in the area. The result of this study will be useful as a database of coral reef species in Bohol. This will also be necessary for continuous conservation and monitoring in the area.

Objectives of the Study

The study generally focused on identifying the coral species in Silo-Siloan Islet. This study also directs to the abundance of each coral species found in the area. Lastly, the study ought to know how diverse each species is relative to the identified sites.

II. METHODOLOGY

Study Site

Figure 1. Map of the Philippines, Bohol and Sampling Sites (Google Earth, 2018)

Bohol is an island province of the Philippines in the Central Visayas region which is famous for its biodiversity (Figure 1). There are several coastal areas of the province and one of which is Clarin located at 9° 57' 43" North, 124° 1' 25" East. It is the fifth-class municipality in the province.

Sampling Method

The line transect was the method used to assess the distribution and abundance of flora and fauna along the shore (English *et al.*, 1997). At 5 meters intervals along the line transect, ten quadrats measuring 1x1 m were placed. There were 3 transects with 100m long that were deployed in each site for a total of 9 transects. The starting point of the line transect was randomly selected along the area. Two sampling areas were selected during the assessment. The first sampling area was inside the mangrove ecosystem and the second sampling area was outside the mangrove ecosystem. Specimens collected in the study sites were identified down to the species level using different references, web searches, and previous studies.

Physico-chemical parameters of seawater were recorded such as temperature, salinity, pH, and dissolved oxygen (DO) during sampling. Dissolved oxygen (DO) and temperature were measured using DO portable meter for field monitoring. Salinity was obtained by the use of a refractometer. Digital pH meter (Suntex) was used to measure the pH of seawater.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1. Species Composition of Corals in Silo-Siloan Islet, Clarin, Bohol

Species Name	Class	Order	Family	No. of Individuals
<i>Acropora splendida</i>	Anthozoa	Scleractinia	Acroporidae	130
<i>Acropora insignis</i>	Anthozoa	Scleractinia	Acroporidae	80
<i>Acropora loricata</i>	Anthozoa	Scleractinia	Acroporidae	2
<i>Porites cylindrica</i>	Anthozoa	Scleractinia	Poritidae	95
<i>Psammocora digitata</i>	Anthozoa	Scleractinia	Psammocoridae	50
<i>Millepora alaicornis</i>	Hydrozoa	Anthoathecata	Milleporidae	2
<i>Pocillopora verrucosa</i>	Anthozoa	Scleractinia	Pocilloporidae	277
<i>Leptoria phrygia</i>	Anthozoa	Scleractinia	Merulinidae	41
<i>Porites brighami</i>	Anthozoa	Scleractinia	Poritidae	26
<i>Echinopora lamellosa</i>	Anthozoa	Scleractinia	Merulinidae	17
<i>Turbinaria reniformis</i>	Anthozoa	Scleractinia	Dendrophylliidae	7
<i>Turbinaria peltata</i>	Anthozoa	Scleractinia	Dendrophylliidae	17
<i>Pavona frondifera</i>	Anthozoa	Scleractinia	Acroporidae	17
<i>Fungia fungites</i>	Anthozoa	Scleractinia	Fungiidae	2
<i>Pectinia lactuca</i>	Anthozoa	Scleractinia	Merulinidae	2
<i>Sarcophyton elegans</i>	Anthozoa	Alcyonacea	Alcyoniidae	3
<i>Favites halicora</i>	Anthozoa	Scleractinia	Merulinidae	2
<i>Cycloseris patelliformis</i>	Anthozoa	Scleractinia	Fungiidae	2

Table 1 above showed the species of corals that are found in the islet. There were 18 species of corals identified as follows: *Acropora splendida*, *Acropora insignis*, *Acropora loricata*, *Porites cylindrica*,

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Psammocora digitata, *Millepora alcicornis*, *Pocillopora verrucosa*, *Leptoria Phrygia*, *Porites brighami*, *Echinopora lamellosa*, *Turbinaria reniformis*, *Turbinaria peltata*, *Pavona frondifera*, *Fungia fungites*, *Pectinia lactuca*, *Sarcophyton elegans*, *Favites halicora* and *Cycloseris patelliformis* (Appendix A). Among the 18 species of corals, the highest in a number of colonies observed was *Pocillopora verrucosa* with 277 individuals. These species of corals are extremely common in shallower areas from fringing reefs to exposed reefs which could be the reason also why they are the most abundant in the area (Veron, 1986). The second most observed coral species was *Acropora splendida* with 130 number of individuals. They are species that mostly occur in shallow areas exposed to wave action or currents (Wallace, 1999). Considering Silo-Siloan is an islet, there is always wave action observed in the area which could be a reason for their abundance. The third most abundant coral species are the *Porites cylindrica* with 90 individuals. These species of corals were also observed in shallow areas, as described in the study of Montebon and Yap, 1995. Meanwhile, the other remaining coral species which are of a low number of individuals observed are coral species that prefer deep areas of the reef. It was astonishing that these corals were observed in shallow areas probably because of illegal fishing (Bailey, 2015) which are also rampant in the area based on personal interviews.

Abundance of Corals

Figure 2. Abundance of Coral Species in Silo-Siloan Islet

Among the 18 species of corals, the highest in the number of colonies observed was *Pocillopora verrucosa* with 37% (Figure 2). These species of corals are extremely common in Pacific waters especially in shallow areas about even less than 10 meters deep (De Palmas et al., 2018). They are one of the dominant species (dai and Horng, 2009) which could be the reason for their high abundance. The second most observed coral species was *Acropora splendida* with 19% abundance. These species occupy a wide array of habitats (Done, 1982) which could be the reason why they are abundant in the area. Third abundant species are *Porites cylindrica* (12%) which could be because they are highly dependent on irradiance in shallow areas which are observed in the study (Montebon and Yap, 1995). Other species of corals prefer to live in mesophotic environments which could be why they have a lower abundance (Loya et al., 2019).

Table 2. Biodiversity of Coral Species

Sites	No. of Individuals	Shannon Weiner Diversity Index (H)	Simpson Diversity Index (D)
A (inside mangal area)	628	1.8	2.44
B (outside mangal area)	144	1.6	3.22

Table 2 showed the biodiversity of coral species. In general, the higher the value of the Shannon diversity index(H) the higher the diversity of communities. However, in Simpson’s Diversity index, the higher the value the less variation in communities and dominance by single taxa. Based on the result between two sites, coral species found inside the mangrove ecosystem Site A (1.8) were of higher diversity compared to Site B (1.7).

Nonetheless, for the Simpson Diversity index, it showed that Site B had more dominant species and less variation. This result also showed that coral species that are highly associated within the mangrove ecosystem are more diverse compared to those corals found outside the mangal area. This phenomenon was supported in the study of Camp et al., 2016 wherein they discovered that corals within mangrove-dominated habitats were thus pre-conditioned to low pH but with significant suppression to calcification ($70.0 \pm 7.3\%$ reduction relative to the outer-reef). Here we report, for the first time, the biological costs for corals living in reef-associated habitats and characterize the environmental services these habitats may play in potentially mitigating the local effects of future ocean acidification.

IV. CONCLUSION

The result of the study showed that Silo-Siloan Islet is a home of diverse corals species. It was also observed that mangrove ecosystems play a big role in ecosystem services as a habitat potential for corals to be more resilient in climate change.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Future study in the monitoring of the physico-chemical parameters such as light intensity, dissolved oxygen, temperature and pH is necessary to know the effect of these physico-chemical parameter changes towards coral growth and diversity.
2. Monitoring water quality is also important to determine its effect on coral growth.
3. Restoration and preservation of corals in the area are highly recommended due to the developing corals present in the area, which can be a potential tourist spot in the future.

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APPENDIX A- Coral Species in Silo-Siloan Islet, Clarin, Bohol

Fig. 3) *Acropora splendida* (Nemanzo,1967)

Fig. 4) *Acropora insignis* (Nemanzo,1967)

Fig.5) *Acropora loricata* (Nemanzo, 1967)

Fig. 6) *Porites cylindrica* (Dana, 1846)

Fig.7) *Psammocora digitata* (Edwards & Haime, 1984)

Fig.8) *Millepora alcicornis*(Linneaus, 1758)

Fig. 9) *Pocillopora verrucosa* (Ellis and Solander, 1786)

Fig.10) *Leptoria phrygia* (Ellis and Solander, 1786)

Fig. 11) *Porolithothamnion* (Lamarck, 1807)

Fig. 12) *Echinopora lamellosa* (Lamarck, 1816)

Figure 13. *Turbinaria reniformis* (Bernard, 1896)

Figure 13. *Turbinaria peltata* (Esper, 1794)

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<p>Fig.15) <i>Fungia fungites</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)</p>	
<p>Fig. 17) <i>Sarcophyton elegans</i> (Moser, 1919)</p>	
<p>Fig.19) <i>Cycloseris patelliformis</i> (Milne-Edwards & Haime, 1849)</p>	